

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF GEO-AGE FACTORS IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. This article focuses on the analysis of the role of political, economic, natural, cultural factors in the history of mankind, as well as geo-Asian factors in its development processes. In the teaching of socio-political sciences, a lot of attention is paid to the nature of geopolitics, methods, geopolitical factors, aspects of the science, and its relationship with other socio-political sciences. The main ideas and principles of representatives of the classical school of geopolitics are highlighted. In the analysis of geopolitical processes, the methods of analysis and synthesis, historicity and logic, comparative comparison, and generalization are appropriately used.

Key words: geopolitics, political geography, political science, national interest, geographical environment, geopolitical factor, demography.

Every state, kingdom, and civilization that was born in any region of the world was caused by a number of natural, geographical, political, economic, social, cultural, and religious factors. Although geopolitics as a science appeared in a new era, geopolitical interests and geopolitical movements have a long history. Because as the first geopoliticians, different rulers appeared in different eras. Geopolitics is recognized as an idea in the sense that the theoretical discussions put forward by a number of geopolitical schools reflected the ideas about the world and determined the policy pursued by one or another country. Geopolitics as a method expressed the essence of knowledge of scientific and pedagogical importance.

True, until the 90s of the 20th century, the communist ideology considered geopolitics a political concept that uses geographical evidence and factors (the country's territory, location, etc.) to justify imperialist expansion, connecting its basis with racism, Malthusianism, and social-Darwinism. has been evaluated negatively by 'rifling'. However, developments over the next decade have given rise to new approaches to geopolitics, and have shown that geopolitics is a complete reflection of the ideas that the former Soviet science had promoted.

Geopolitics considers the state not as a stable, static phenomenon, but as a dynamic - changing social phenomenon. Although he does not use the word "geopolitics" in his works, the German scientist Friedrich Ratzel (1844-1940) can

be said to be the "father" of the science of geopolitics. In his time, Ratzel was widely involved in the sciences of sociology and geography. He named his main work published in 1897 "Political Geography" ("Politische Geographie"). Although F. Ratzel expressed his subjective opinions about political geography, his comments were of direct geopolitical importance. In particular, the scientist does not support the priority of geographical factors in state activity and opinions about their immutability. According to him, the state is a "living organism" that lives in constant excitement (3. 35-b). According to F. Ratzel, geopolitics, unlike political geography, is not primarily interested in the location of the state, its climate and forms.

The term "geopolitics" was first used in scientific circles by the Swedish scientist Rudolf Chellen (1864-1922) in his work entitled "The State as a Form of Life" ("Der Staat als Lebensform", 1916). The scientist defines geopolitics as follows, that is, "geopolitics is a science that studies existing states as a geographical organism or a phenomenon in space." Also, geopolitics "... is the fundamental study of space, and the study is related to the Earth and its minerals. This, in turn, means the study of the formation of empires, the emergence of countries, and the study of the territories of states" (4 17-b).

A unique definition of geopolitics is timely entitled Zeitschrift fuer Geopolitik given in a German journal: Geopolitics is the study of the relationship between the earth and political processes. It should be noted here that the subjects of the political process are unknown. Geopolitics has a geographical foundation. Also, geopolitics is based on political geography, a science that studies existing political organisms and their structure. The purpose of geopolitics is to provide political action with the necessary tools and to guide political life in general. In this sense, geopolitics can be called the science of practical political management. Geopolitics is the geographical intelligence of the state (5. 9-b). According to the Russian geopolitician N. Nartov, geopolitics is an intermediate science and does not have a specific field of research. When he pays more attention to politics and political events, he summarizes them based on geographical factors and aspects. On the other hand, geopolitics widely uses a number of geographical factors in explaining and justifying the internal and external policies of the state: border definition, wealth of natural minerals and resources, convenience of the island or land on which it is located, climate, relief, etc. For many years, as a decisive factor in geopolitics, the expansion of the metropolis in the geographical space has become the main importance. Over time, this factor began to give way to peaceful, egalitarian relations between countries.

Many researchers consider geopolitics as a science that studies geographical, historical, political, cultural and other factors that influence the geostrategic power

of a state. Russian geopolitician V. Dergachev, comparing geopolitics and political geography, considers political geography as a science that studies the influence of the environment, spatial opportunities, features on the development of political processes. According to Y. Tikhonravov, geopolitics is a field of science that studies the laws of interaction of non-political systems created by the geographical environment - territory, environment, climate, landscape, minerals, ecology, demography, etc. Some try to prove that geopolitics is a science that studies the military-political, cultural and economic factors in a society, a certain region or a country. N. Starikov tries to explain what this science studies based on this formula:

geopolitics= politics+history+geography (6. 8-b).

In general, studies related to geopolitics and the definitions given in relation to it can be conditionally analyzed as follows. These are:

Track 1: Emphasis is placed on the relationship between political geography and politics. Those in this direction look to geography as a primary factor and argue that it has greater influence on politics;

Direction 2: more attention is paid to the struggle of political power centers for power in a particular region or world. Those in this direction mainly emphasize interstate competition and discuss the universal features of science;

Direction 3: a comprehensive approach to geopolitics, that is, the presence of researchers who, in addition to geographic factors, have a broad approach to economic, demographic, religious and other similar factors, researched and conducted.

As can be seen from the mentioned general views, geopolitics differs sharply from political geography, or a number of disciplines, in terms of its method and its object. Its practice is not limited to geographical factors in society. Also, geopolitics in its practice considers various political, economic, religious, military, geographical factors as a constant and changing process

Geopolitical factors are divided into permanent and variable factors according to their content. Permanent geographical factors include the territorial location of a state or region, the shape and extent (relative) of its borders, climate, topography, flora and fauna, and so on. Variable geographical factors refer to the population, mineral resources, political culture and social structure of a region or country. In general, the main geopolitical factors are manifested in the following forms:

- territorial factor ;
- political factor - the political structure of the state, its characteristics, social strata in the state, borders of the state, etc. ;

- geographical factor - location, natural resources, fauna , flora and so on ;
- economic factor - the standard of living of the population, the power of productive forces , materials, market development level , etc .;
- transport - communication opportunity - strategic location, railway, highways, river-water transport, etc.;
- natural climatic conditions;
- cultural factor - national traditions, cultural values, level of development of science and education, etc .;
- demographic factor - population composition , location, population growth rate, etc .;
- the strength and military training of the military forces, the level of training of military specialists , etc .;
- ecological factor is the attitude of the population to the limitation of natural resources of states and regions, the reduction of raw material reserves , etc .;

It can be seen that geopolitics is very broad and multi - faceted in terms of its scope as a subject of study . The scope of modern geopolitics is directly and indirectly related to the factors of world politics, the problem of power and the dominant ideologies in society. In this sense, geopolitics can be defined as a science that studies management problems in society . In addition, geopolitics as a science incorporates the characteristics of a number of independent sciences and scientific fields that study the above-mentioned factors . These are geography, political science, history, ethnography, religious studies, ecology, history of ideologies, sociology, theory and practice of military knowledge, demography, etc. It can be seen that geopolitics is not just a science, but an interdisciplinary science system that combines the characteristics of many disciplines and analyzes the methods and tools that ensure the realization of its goals and tasks . Based on the above considerations, geopolitics can be defined as follows: **Geopolitics is** a science that examines and studies geographical, historical, political, economic and other interrelated factors that affect the strategic power of the state and ensure its priority interests in domestic and foreign policy. . Integrating political, historical, economic, legal and geographical processes, geopolitics is not a mere phenomenon added to military or diplomatic history. Geopolitics, while mastering them, manifests itself in their harmonization in the realization of national interests. Prospects of geopolitics as a separate field of research, training, and way of looking at the world show their relevance in the following cases:

First of all, the study of geopolitical processes is important in forming the democratic political culture of the society, in getting rid of the thinking of the population from the way

of thinking typical of the empire, in understanding the essence of radical geopolitical actions;

Secondly, geopolitical paradigms, as a separate type of activity, are of great importance in the multipolar world where new geopolitical processes are taking place, in the world community;

Thirdly, in front of the emerging science of geopolitics, there are issues such as mastering the achievements of Western geopolitics, identifying its main trends, studying the development features of current geopolitical processes, the solution of which lies in determining the status of Uzbekistan in Central Asia and the world community. is of special importance.

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